

Staying on track: a bottom-up Paris-aligned pathway driven by COP initiatives

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ABSTRACT

The announcement of voluntary climate initiatives during recent Conferences of Parties (COPs) underscores the interplay between voluntary initiatives and the outcomes of the Global Stocktake and COP decisions. Harmonising the collective stocktake efforts with initiative goals facilitates developing pathways across specific thematic areas (e.g., sectors, greenhouse gases) towards achieving the Paris Agreement goals. The effectiveness of the initiatives is assessed by calculating their potential impact on greenhouse gas emissions, assuming full implementation by the signatories. Their alignment with the Paris temperature goals is assessed against 2 °C and 1.5 °C pathways. Two scenarios, based on signatory and full global participation, are compared with current policy scenarios and pathways consistent with below 2 °C and 1.5 °C (high overshoot). If country signatories implemented initiative targets domestically, projections for 2030 to 2050 are generally more ambitious than current policies, potentially decreasing global emissions by about 11%. Comparing full global implementation to below 2 °C or 1.5 °C pathways, the results are mixed. By 2030, most initiative goals align with 2 °C, but certain thematic areas are missing. A number of initiatives demonstrate ambition beyond 1.5 °C pathways, questioning their feasibility. Achieving all global initiative targets by 2030 consistent with the below 2 °C and 1.5 °C (high overshoot) pathways requires 5–8% additional reductions. Realising the full potential of these initiatives necessitates increasing ambition for specific goals by 2030, increasing and clarifying long-term ambition, expanding thematic coverage, and requiring concrete climate action plans. Within the UNFCCC, this can be facilitated by making Global Stocktake goals more explicit, based on COP initiatives.

1. Introduction

The first Global Stocktake of the Paris Agreement concluded that the world is not on track to hold global average temperature increase to well below 2 °C above pre-industrial levels and to pursue efforts to limit it to 1.5 °C increase, and therefore calls for deeper emissions reductions, especially before 2030 [51]. This statement reflects the insufficiency of collective ambition by 2030 from implemented current policies and Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) intended to achieve the global temperature goals [12,44]. Without stronger climate action, the world will overshoot the Paris temperature limits, which might not be reversible within a few decades [45]. To this end, the outcomes of the Global Stocktake included eight global goals through which countries can contribute to keeping the world on a 1.5 °C pathway [51], see Table 1.

At the same time, a growing number of initiatives focusing on climate mitigation have been launched in the context of the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC). The Brazilian COP30 presidency is committed to reinforcing climate initiatives with a focus on concrete and already existing initiatives, which is part of their motto "mutirão", which refers to a community working together on a task [11]. These COP initiatives are a subset of international voluntary climate initiatives that are launched at the Conference of Parties (COPs). They bring together countries, cities, regions, and companies to take climate action, often organised around specific thematic areas such as sectors, greenhouse gases or technologies, and are often centred around an overarching mitigation goal [54]. In addition to displaying ambition, these initiatives provide opportunities for countries as well as non-state and subnational actors to showcase good

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Table 1

The Global Stocktake goals and Conferences of Parties (COP) initiatives targeting the same area of climate mitigation. The translation of the 'tripling renewable energy and doubling energy efficiency' goals to capacity and energy intensity improvements were retrieved from IRENA et al. [24].

Global Stocktake document, paragraphs 28 and 33 [51]	Short form of stocktake goal	COP Initiative	Initiative goal
(28a) Tripling renewable energy capacity globally and doubling the global average annual rate of energy efficiency improvements by 2030	Tripling renewable energy, Doubling energy efficiency	(COP28) Global renewables and energy efficiency pledge (Tripling Renewable, Doubling Efficiency)	Tripling renewable energy capacity by 2030, or at least 11,200 GW, and doubling the global average annual rate of energy efficiency improvements from around 2 % to over 4 % per year until 2030
(28b) Accelerating efforts towards the phase-down of unabated coal power	Phase down unabated coal power	(COP26) Global Coal to Clean Power Transition + Breakthrough Agenda (coal)	Transition away from unabated coal power generation in the 2030s (or as soon as possible thereafter) for major economies and in the 2040s globally
(28c) Accelerating efforts globally towards net zero emission energy systems, utilizing zero- and low-carbon fuels well before or by around mid-century	Net-zero emission energy systems	(COP26) International Aviation Climate Ambition Coalition	In line with 1.5 °C pathways
(28d) Transitioning away from fossil fuels in energy systems, in a just, orderly and equitable manner, accelerating action in this critical decade, so as to achieve net zero by 2050 in keeping with the science	Transitioning away from fossil fuels	(COP28) Global cooling pledge	Net zero emissions from cooling by 2050, e.g., through passive cooling
(28e) Accelerating zero- and low-emission technologies, including, inter alia, renewables, nuclear, abatement and removal technologies such as carbon capture and utilization and storage, particularly in hard-to-abate sectors, and low-carbon hydrogen production	Accelerating zero- and low-emission technologies	(COP26) COP26 Breakthrough Agenda on steel (COP28) COP28 Breakthrough Agenda on cement	Near-zero emission steel is the preferred choice in global markets, with efficient use and near-zero emission steel production established and growing in all regions by 2030. Near-zero emission cement is the preferred choice in global markets, with efficient use and near-zero emission cement production by 2030.
(28f) Accelerating and substantially reducing non-carbon-dioxide emissions globally, including methane emissions by 2030	Reducing non-carbon-dioxide emissions	(COP26) Global Methane Pledge	Reduce global methane emissions by at least 30 % by 2030, compared to a 2020 baseline
(28g) Accelerating the reduction of emissions from road transport on a range of pathways, including through development of infrastructure and rapid deployment of zero- and low-emission vehicles	Accelerating reductions road transport emissions	(COP26) COP26 Declaration on Accelerating the transition to 100 % zero emissions cars and vans + Breakthrough Agenda (transport) (COP26) Global Memorandum of Understanding for Zero-emissions Medium- and Heavy-Duty Vehicles (COP28) Oil & Gas Decarbonization Charter	100 % zero emissions car/van sales by 2040 (2035 in leading markets) 100 % zero emission new truck and bus sales by 2040
(28h) Phasing out inefficient fossil fuel subsidies that do not address energy poverty or just transitions, as soon as possible	Phasing out inefficient fossil fuel subsidies		1. Reach net zero emissions by 2050 or earlier 2. Zero-out methane emissions 3. Eliminate routine flaring by 2030
(33) Conserving, protecting, and restoring nature and ecosystems towards achieving the Paris Agreement temperature goal, including through enhanced efforts towards halting and reversing deforestation and forest degradation by 2030	Halting deforestation	(COP26) Glasgow Leaders' Declaration on Forests and land use	Halting and reversing forest loss and land degradation by 2030

practices [14].

Comparison of the launched COP initiatives with the outcomes of the Global Stocktake and COP decisions reveals an evolving interplay between them. The aspirational goals from the COP initiatives regularly proliferate into the COP decisions and the outcomes of the global stocktake [50,51], see Table 1. Combined, they can demonstrate what global ambition is needed to implement the Paris goals in specific thematic areas. Most of the Global Stocktake goals do not specify concrete targets, including a clear indicator and target year. However, the signatories of the COP initiatives reveal explicit targets for specific thematic areas, which are intended to align with the Paris goals. This shows that the concrete goals of the COP initiatives could make the Global Stocktake goals more specific. For example, the transport initiatives with specific goals for low carbon cars, buses and trucks can link to the less concrete global stocktake goal aiming to accelerate the reduction of emissions from road transport.

To date, there has not been a systematic assessment of the combined effects of the COP initiatives and linkages with the Global Stocktake goals. There have been several assessments of individual initiatives, which indicate that the goals can be considered highly ambitious. Malley et al. [29] showed that the Global Methane Pledge (GMP) can only be achieved if mitigation measures implemented by participating countries significantly exceed their current potential. Analyses of the Tripling Renewable, Doubling Efficiency (3R2E) initiative show that its goal is

aligned with the IRENA 1.5 °C scenario. In addition, existing studies highlight the potential and high ambition of a broader set of climate initiatives assuming full alignment with 1.5 °C pathways [26].

However, none of these studies provide a comprehensive picture of the combined effect of the implementation of the key initiatives' goals, their interactions, and their level of alignment with the Paris Agreement. As such, it has also been unclear to which degree thematic areas are covered by the initiatives and to which degree the initiatives help align current climate action with the overall goals of the Paris Agreement. Therefore, this study addresses key gaps in literature by quantitatively assessing the combined impact of implemented COP initiatives launched at COP26 in Glasgow and COP28 in Dubai. Using the IMAGE 3.4 integrated assessment modelling framework allows us to evaluate their impacts and their alignment with the climate goals of the Paris Agreement across geographic and sectoral scales. Moreover, the use of an integrated model allows for the assessment of interactions between initiatives, providing a more comprehensive understanding of their potential outcomes.

More specifically, this study addresses three key questions: 1) What is the total impact on GHG emissions at sectoral and global levels if current initiatives signatories fully implement their initiative commitments? 2) Do the initiative goals align with 2 °C and 1.5 °C scenarios by 2030 and 2050? 3) Which thematic areas are missing? Note that although the 1.5 °C limit is most likely exceeded before 2035 as the

current global human induced warming over the period 2014–2023 is 1.19 °C and increasing at a rate of 0.26 °C per decade [16,38], this goal could still serve as a benchmark for evaluating progress in climate action.

To assess the contribution of initiatives and the consistency of initiative goals with the Paris temperature targets, we translated the initiatives' goals into model targets and implemented them in the IMAGE model. For this purpose, we developed scenarios representing the potential combined impact of these initiatives and compared them with existing scenarios consistent with the 1.5 °C and 2 °C climate goals, as well as a scenario representing current implemented national climate policies.

It should be noted that the implementation processes for the aspirational goals of voluntary climate initiatives are less stringent than those of national governments, which often embed such goals in law. They are also less formalised than the process around Nationally Determined Contributions, which are subject to a five-year Global Stocktake to monitor progress and strengthen ambition. The voluntary pledges made under these initiatives merely indicate the direction that actors aspire to take; however, their progress, integrity, feasibility, and credibility remain uncertain. These aspects warrant further research building on the results of this study, which focuses on what the implementation of these ambitions could achieve. However, to provide an indication of progress, we added historical data to show global or sectoral trends where possible.

2. Methods

To assess the global and sectoral impact of COP initiatives based on their stated goals, we have selected mitigation initiatives launched at COP 26 and COP28, translated their goals to model input, and developed scenarios to assess both the impact and Paris alignment of the initiative goals.

2.1. Collecting and selecting COP initiatives

This study includes climate initiatives announced in the lead-up to or at the COPs from 2021 to 2024 (Table 2). Although other international climate initiatives have been initiated outside the COP events [10], these were not included in this analysis. The included initiatives were announced around COP26 and COP28 and have pledged quantifiable targets which were published on the respective event websites (see Table 2 and Supplementary Material). At COP27 in Sharm El-Sheikh and COP29 in Baku, no mitigation initiatives were announced with clear and quantifiable targets. 'Quantifiable' refers to energy or land use targets with clearly defined base year, target year, and target year reduction, that have a direct impact on greenhouse gas emissions.

It should be noted that not including the initiatives of COP27 and COP29, does not imply that they are ineffective, but their aims cannot be directly translated into measurable mitigation outcomes. They instead may serve different functions, such as training or campaigning [7,9]. In addition, they support the energy transition to low-carbon efforts focused on improving the energy system, such as hydrogen development, scaling-up electricity grids, or addressing finance and adaptation. For example, the higher storage ambitions outlined in the COP29 Global Energy Storage and Grid pledge indirectly support the deployment of renewable technologies with intermittent supply such as solar and wind, thereby contributing to the renewable energy target from the Triple Renewable and Double Efficiency initiative. A similar synergy exists for the Hydrogen goal under the Breakthrough Agenda, which aims to make affordable renewable and low-carbon hydrogen globally available by 2030. This goal supports the development of low-carbon steel making within the same initiative, as well as the introduction of hydrogen cars, buses and trucks promoted through the COP26 Declaration on Accelerating the transition to 100 % zero emissions cars and vans, the Breakthrough Agenda road transport, and COP26 Global Memorandum

of Understanding for Zero-emissions Medium- and Heavy-Duty Vehicles.

Thirteen initiatives with quantifiable goals were selected (see the Supplementary Material for details showing the sources and selection of initiatives). From these initiatives, two were combined as 'Passenger Transport initiative' and two as 'Coal Phase-out initiative' because the pledged goals were similar (see Table 2). For each of the eleven resulting initiatives, we collected the overall initiatives mitigation goals, and the participating countries based on the signatories listed on the COP and initiative websites. Although we also identified the signatory cities, regions, and companies (non-state actors), these are not explicitly included in the analysis. A few initiatives are part of the Glasgow Breakthrough Agenda which brings together several initiatives [21]. However, except for the Steel and the Cement Breakthrough, we either combined these with already selected initiatives (Coal phase-out and Passenger transport) or excluded them due to no signatories (agriculture) or a lack of quantifiable targets (hydrogen, buildings). Another initiative is the Oil & Gas Decarbonization Charter that includes oil companies as members and accounts for 43 % of global oil production [35]. We only included the 'eliminate flaring by 2030' goal from this initiative, as the other goals were either insufficiently concrete or already covered by the Methane Pledge.

The selected initiatives differ in three key aspects: economic sector coverage, GHG emissions coverage, and country signatories. In terms of economic sector coverage, they often span multiple subsectors within the main sectors such as electricity production, oil production, industry, transport, residential, agriculture, land use, land-use change and forestry (LULUCF), and international transport (see Supplementary Table 1). Some initiatives overlap in their thematic areas, such as the Coal Phase-out initiative, 3R2E initiative, and Cooling Pledge, which all target the electricity production sector. Key sectors, such as industry (excluding steel/cement) and buildings (except for cooling) were largely unaddressed. Regarding GHG emissions coverage, most initiatives primarily impact CO₂ emissions. The exception is the Global Methane Pledge which exclusively targets CH₄ emissions. The initiatives collectively address 71.8 % of total global GHG emissions in 2020 (see Supplementary Table 2). The missing emissions sources are primarily agricultural N₂O and F-gases. Finally, in terms of country signatories, the collected signatories for each initiative can be found in the Supplementary Material.

2.2. Model implementation of initiatives' goals and scenarios

The assessment in this study is conducted with the IMAGE 3.4 model [47,53], an integrated assessment model that simulates the interaction between human activities and the earth system over the longer term (see Supplementary Material for details). This model provides a detailed representation of energy and land use systems across 26 large regions, with the single countries USA, China, Japan, India, Russia, Canada, Brazil, Mexico, and Indonesia each constituting one region, while Europe is divided into the regions of Western and Central Europe.

To assess the global impact of implementing the COP initiatives' goals, we use normative scenarios, which describe possible pathways toward achieving a desired future state. Scenarios provide the overarching storyline, including potential policy goals, while pathways display the modelled trajectories over time (e.g. emissions or energy use) to achieve the desired scenario outcomes [22,39]. Specifically, we developed COP initiative scenarios and compared their projected pathways between 2020 and 2050 with published current policies and Paris temperature aligned scenarios [12,32,37], see Table 3. This approach implies that the results do not address the likelihood of achieving these desired states, which would require explorative scenarios (see Discussion and conclusions).

The *Current Policies* scenario illustrates the impact of implemented climate mitigation policies defined by legislative decisions or executive orders [42]. The *Below 2 °C scenario* (>66 %) represents a globally cost-effective pathway from 2023 onward that is consistent with

Table 2

Voluntary Climate Initiatives announced at COP26 and COP28 with clear and quantifiable targets, which have a clear base year, target year and target percentage change. Including number of signatories, sector, and GHG coverage in 2020 (European Commission [15], and Supplementary Table 1).

COP Initiative	Short name	Nr. of signatory countries	Coverage (main sector, subsector)	Greenhouse gas coverage (as % of total emissions in 2020)
(COP28) Global renewables and energy efficiency pledge (Triple Renewable, Double Efficiency (para 28a))	3R2E initiative • Renewable pledge • Efficiency pledge	154	Energy supply - electricity production • Renewables Energy supply/demand • Efficiency	CO ₂ (26.6 %)
(COP26) Global Coal to Clean Power Transition (COP26) Breakthrough Agenda (coal) (para 28b)	Coal Phase-out initiative	60	Energy supply - electricity production • Coal	CO ₂ (17.5 %)
(COP26) International Aviation Climate Ambition Coalition (para 28c)	International Aviation initiative	62	International transport • International aviation	CO ₂ (0.6 %)
(COP28) Global cooling pledge (para 28d)	Cooling Pledge	160	Residential electricity consumption • Cooling	CO ₂ (1.8 %)
(COP26) Breakthrough Agenda on steel (para 28e)	Steel Breakthrough	38	Industry • Steel	CO ₂ (7.3 %)
(COP28) COP28 Breakthrough Agenda on cement (para 28e)	Cement Breakthrough	34	Industry • Cement	CO ₂ (3.1 %)
(COP26) Global Methane Pledge (para 28f)	Methane Pledge	160	Energy supply (fossil), Residential, Industry, Agriculture, LULUCF	CH ₄ (17.9 %)
(COP26) COP26 Declaration on Accelerating the transition to 100 % zero emissions cars and vans (COP26) Breakthrough Agenda (transport) (para 28 g)	Passenger Transport initiative	50	Transport • Passenger (cars, buses)	CO ₂ (8.3 %)
(COP26) Global Memorandum of Understanding for Zero-emissions Medium- and Heavy-Duty Vehicles (para 28 g)	Trucks initiative	37	Transport • Trucks	CO ₂ (2.3 %)
(COP28) Oil & Gas Decarbonization Charter (para 28h)	Flaring initiative		Energy supply - oil production • Flaring	CO ₂ (0.8 %)
(COP26) Glasgow Leaders' Declaration on Forests and land use (para 33)	Deforestation initiative	144	Land use • Deforestation	CO ₂ (5.8 %)
TOTAL				CO ₂ , CH ₄ (71.8 %)

limiting global temperature increase since the industrial period below 2 °C with at least 66 % probability (based on the assessment of uncertainty in the climate system), while the Below 1.5 °C high overshoot (>50 %) scenario assumes at least 50 % chance of returning warming to 1.5 °C by the end of the century after a high overshoot. The 1.5 °C scenario with limited overshoot was not feasible in the IMAGE model. The *Below 2 °C scenario* (>66 %) is consistent with the C3 scenarios from the IPCC AR6 scenario database, and the Below 1.5 °C high overshoot (>50 %) with the C2 scenarios. The IMAGE model results were compared with GHG emissions from these C2-C3 scenarios, based on 11-13 models and 99–177 scenarios that reported all economic sectors and greenhouse gases [5]. For each scenario, the models incorporated multiple variables, though the number of variables varied across scenarios. Supplementary Figure 1 compares the IMAGE scenarios used in this study with the IMAGE scenarios included in the IPCC AR6 database.

In addition, two COP Initiative scenarios were developed: the *Global Climate Initiatives* scenario, assuming full global implementation of the initiative goals, and the *Signatories Climate Initiatives* scenario, reflecting implementation exclusively by the signatories of the initiatives.

The *Global Climate Initiatives* scenario was developed by implementing the global initiative goals in addition to the *Current policies* scenario, either by translating the targets into model targets and adjusting IMAGE model input parameters, or by imposing carbon taxes on specific sub-sectors or technologies (see Supplementary Table 2 for details). To implement the aspirational initiative goals, we distinguished between high-income and middle/low-income countries, with the latter assumed to achieve targets 5 to 10 years later (see Supplementary Table 3 and Supplementary Table 4). If the target year of an initiative goal is before 2050, equivalent efforts were assumed to continue at the regional level. For example, the goal from the International Aviation initiative was translated into a model target based on the ambitious scenario from the ICAO report (2022), which assumes 65 % CO₂ reduction between 2019 and 2050. The efficiency improvement goal for

3R2E scenario was calculated using IRENA [23], which projects an absolute renewable capacity of 11,000 GW by 2030 and energy efficiency as the annual improvement of energy intensity per unit of GDP, with a doubling of efficiency corresponding to a 4 % annual improvement until 2030. The capacity target and efficiency improvement were set as minimum targets after 2030.

The Signatories Climate Initiatives scenario was developed by downscaling the emissions pathways from the Global Climate Initiative scenario to account for initiative signatory countries only. Downscaling allocates regional emissions to finer spatial units, such as countries. This study used a simple downscaling method and calculated the share of the 2021 historical GHG emissions covered by the signatory countries. The year 2021 marked the starting point of most of the COP initiatives. If no historical country data was available, other relevant indicators were used (see Supplementary Table 5). This share was calculated for each IMAGE region and held constant over the period from 2020 to 2050. For each initiative and its specific thematic area, a GHG emissions pathway was constructed by assuming that country signatories follow the pathway from the Global Climate Initiatives scenario, while other countries follow the Current Policies scenario. As the Coal phase-out initiative, 3R2E initiative, and the Cooling pledge overlap in the electricity production sector, we used the largest absolute downscaled reduction in each country to represent the total reductions in that sector. If a country is a member of all three initiatives, total reductions from the Global Climate Initiatives scenario (for that country) in the electricity sector were used. The flaring initiative was downscaled assuming that the 43 % of global oil production that signatories represent [34] can be translated to the share of CO₂ emissions from flaring.

As the likelihood of achieving the goals of voluntary climate initiatives may be lower than that of Current Policies, we define three scenarios to illustrate the impact of different assumptions. The first sensitivity consists of the Global GMP/3R2E and Signatories GMP/3R2E scenarios, assuming that only the Global Methane Pledge and the 3R2E

Table 3
Description of scenarios used in this study.

Scenario name	Description
Current Policies	This scenario includes current domestic climate mitigation policies implemented until June 2024, which mostly run up to 2030. The included policies are expected to have a significant impact on greenhouse gas emissions, as supported by literature and national expert opinions. These policies were adopted by national governments through legislation or executive orders, with no evidence of major barriers to their implementation [43]. The impact of the policies is extrapolated after 2030 by using the equivalent model carbon price from 2030.
Below 2 °C (>66 %)	This scenario assumes a global cost-effective implementation of climate policy assuming a radiative forcing target of 2.6 W/m ² by 2100, which is consistent with keeping temperature relative to the industrial period below 2 °C at the end of this century with a 66 % probability (IPCC category C3).
Below 1.5 °C high overshoot (>50 %)	This scenario assumes a global cost-effective implementation of climate policy assuming a radiative forcing target of 1.9 W/m ² by 2100, which is consistent with bringing the temperature below 1.5 °C relative to the industrial period at the end of this century after a high overshoot, with a 50 % probability (IPCC category C2).
Global Climate Initiatives Sensitivities:	This scenario assumes all initiative goals are globally implemented.
- Global GMP/3R2E	The GMP/3R2E variant only includes the goals from the Global Methane Pledge and the Triple Renewable/Double Efficiency initiative.
- Global Climate Initiatives (incl. buildings)	This variant adds one initiative to the Global Climate Initiatives scenario by assuming the buildings' goal from the Breakthrough agenda can be translated to building of zero-emissions new buildings.
Signatories Climate Initiatives Sensitivities:	This scenario includes the aggregated impact of all signatories that signed up to the selected COP initiatives and are assumed to domestically implement the corresponding initiative goal.
- Signatories GMP/3R2E	This scenario includes all signatories of the GMP and 3R2E initiatives.
- Signatories Climate Initiative (excl. USA)	Variant where it is assumed that the US stepped out of the COP initiatives in line with their withdrawal of the Paris Agreement. This scenario adds the signatories from the Breakthrough Buildings to the <i>Signatories Climate Initiatives</i>
- Signatories Climate Initiatives (incl. buildings)	

initiatives are implemented. These two initiatives are included in the outcomes of the Global Stocktake with explicit target years [51], receive the most attention, and are tracked by the IEA [20]. In the second scenario, we assume that the United States does not implement its pledges, reflecting its withdrawal of the Paris Agreement [48]. In the third scenario, we interpret the less specific goal of the Breakthrough Agenda for buildings as achieving new zero-emissions buildings fully equipped with solar panels, heat pumps, and optimal insulation (see Supplementary Table 2. IMAGE implementation of initiatives' goals).

To systematically quantify how the climate initiatives contribute to emissions reductions, total Kyoto greenhouse gas emissions reductions between the Current Policies scenario and the COP initiatives scenario are decomposed into several components. First, total reductions are divided into CO₂ and non-CO₂ emissions (see Eq. (1)). The CO₂ emissions are then further decomposed according to IPAT equation into population (P), GDP (PPP) per capita (GDP), energy intensity (final energy (FE) per GDP), conversion efficiency (primary energy (PE) per final energy), and CO₂ intensity (CO₂ per primary energy unit) (see Eq. (2)). A logarithmic form is applied to ensure that the components sum to the total reductions. The population and GDP (PPP) are exogenous variables in the IMAGE model, and do not differ between scenarios. Further details are provided in the Supplementary Material.

$$\ln\left(\frac{Kyoto_s}{Kyoto_b}\right) = \frac{CO_2^b}{Kyoto_b} \times \ln\left(\frac{CO_2^s}{CO_2^b}\right) + \frac{nonCO_2^b}{Kyoto_b} \times \ln\left(\frac{nonCO_2^s}{nonCO_2^b}\right) \quad (1)$$

$$\ln\left(\frac{CO_2^s}{CO_2^b}\right) = \ln\left(\frac{P^s}{P^b}\right) + \ln\left(\frac{GDP^s/P^s}{GDP^b/P^b}\right) + \ln\left(\frac{FE^s/GDP^s}{FE^b/GDP^b}\right) + \ln\left(\frac{PE^s/FE^s}{PE^b/FE^b}\right) + \ln\left(\frac{CO_2^s/PE^s}{CO_2^b/PE^b}\right) \quad (2)$$

where

- s = COP initiatives scenario
- b = baseline scenario (Current Policies)
- P = population
- GDP = Gross Domestic Product
- FE = Final Energy
- PE = Primary Energy

In addition to assessing impact on GHG emissions and IPAT indicators, we evaluated the Paris alignment of the initiative goals and translated the global goals from the Global Stocktake into indicators available in the IMAGE model (see Supplementary Table 6). These Stocktake goals aim to guide global mitigation efforts toward sectoral or greenhouse gas emissions pathways consistent with the long-term Paris goals [51].

3. Results

We first present an assessment of the sectoral ambitions to evaluate the potential impact of signatories and the alignment of initiative goals with sectoral emissions of the cost-optimal pathways (in IMAGE) for 2 °C and 1.5 °C. This also highlights the areas not covered by the initiatives. Next, we present the global emissions pathways resulting from the mutual implementation of the initiative's goals and evaluate the impact on the Stocktake indicators, which are translated to specific indicators.

3.1. Sectoral results

When comparing sectoral global emission pathways under the *Global Initiatives Signatories* scenario and assuming domestic implementation of initiative targets, projections for 2025 to 2050 for specific sectors are generally more ambitious than those under the *Current Policies* scenario (see Fig. 1). However, relative to model-based cost-optimal pathways consistent with limiting global warming below 1.5 °C (high overshoot), the picture is mixed. After 2035, aggregated signatory ambitions in sectors increasingly fall short of the temperature-aligned pathways due to a lack of long-term ambition and sufficient signatories, except for certain thematic areas where initiatives are very ambitious, such as the flaring emissions from oil production and total methane emissions.

The *Signatories Climate Initiative* scenario results are dependent on the ambition of the initiative, the number of signatories, and the inclusion of high-emitting countries in this thematic area. If the signatories of the 3R2E, coal phase-out, and cooling initiatives were to implement measures in line with their pledged ambitions, global CO₂ emissions by 2030 in the electricity and heat sector would fall beyond those projected under the *Current Policies* scenario and align with a cost-effective 1.5 °C pathway (Fig. 1a). However, after 2035, emissions under the *Signatories Climate Initiatives* scenario become even less ambitious than those required for a *Below 2 °C* pathway. The signatories of the flaring initiative show even greater ambition, with emission levels in the oil production sector initially beyond those of the *Below 1.5 °C high overshoot* pathway, though they fall *Below the 2 °C* pathway after 2040 due to the low number of signatories (Fig. 1b). In the transport sector, emissions pathways under the *Signatories Climate Initiatives* scenario remain in between the *Current Policies* and *Below 2 °C scenarios* to 2050. Until 2035, this is mostly the result of the policies included in the *Current*

Policies scenario, which already result in steep emissions reductions until 2035, and is consistent with the *Below 2 °C and 1.5 °C high overshoot* scenarios (Fig. 1c). In the international transport sector, due to insufficient number of signatories, the aggregated ambition remains between the *Current Policies* and *Below 2 °C* scenario projections over this period (Fig. 1d).

In the industry sector, the steel and cement initiatives decrease emissions by 2030 only around 1.5 % relative to the *Current Policies* scenario due to the small amount of signatories, representing only 20 % and 17 % of steel and cement sector emissions in 2020, respectively (Fig. 1e). No COP initiatives directly target the buildings sector, though the doubling of the efficiency goal from the 3R2E initiative yields a small impact. The deforestation initiative that aims to halt forest loss by 2030 only has a small impact by 2030 as halting deforestation in the short-term risks relocating cropland expansion to non-forested natural areas [40] (Fig. 1f). The Global Methane Pledge, which includes both CH₄ emissions from the agriculture, land use sectors, and energy sector, has a

high number of signatories, representing >60 % of 2021 emissions (Fig. 1g). As a result, emissions in the *Signatories Climate Initiatives* scenario are in line with the 1.5 °C scenario until 2030, but remain above the *Below 2 °C* pathway after 2040 due to continued high CH₄ emissions from countries that have not signed up.

Shifting to the assessment of full global implementation, the resulting emissions pathways from the *Global Climate Initiatives* scenario allow analysis of how effectively these initiatives align with the Paris goals, by comparing them with pathways consistent with limiting warming below 2 °C or 1.5 °C with high overshoot. The main results show that the ambition of the Global Methane Pledge and the COP initiatives in the electricity and heat production, oil production, and international aviation sectors results in emissions reductions that surpass those projected under the *Below 1.5 °C high overshoot* sectoral pathways (see Fig. 1). In contrast, the COP initiatives in the transport, industry and AFOLU sectors are consistent with the 2 °C pathway until 2030 and lack sufficient long-term ambition thereafter.

Fig. 1. Emission pathways under the current policies, Signatories Climate Initiatives, Global Climate Initiatives, below 2 °C. The IMAGE results are compared with the IPCC AR6 database [5]. The scenarios categories are: C1, representing a 50 % probability of limiting global warming to 1.5 °C with limited overshoot; C2, representing 50 % probability of limiting warming to 1.5 °C with high overshoot; and a 67 % probability of limiting warming to below 2 °C [22]. Overshoot refers to temporary exceeding of a specified climate target. Source historical data: CEDS [6], EDGAR [15].

Expanding on the main results, the three COP initiatives targeting CO₂ emissions in the electricity and heat sector (coal phase-out, renewable pledge, cooling pledge) are aligned with the *Below 1.5 °C high overshoot* scenario until 2030, but fall short of the *Below 2 °C* pathway after 2035 as higher ambition is needed (Fig. 1a). A similar trend is observed in the alignment of the goals of the individual COP initiatives (see Supplementary Figure 2). The coal phase-out goal for high-income countries by 2030 and low- and middle-income countries by 2040, and the cooling pledge for 2050 were not viable to implement in the IMAGE model as the reduction potential was insufficient to achieve these goals. This indicates that complementary measures are required. By 2050, achieving alignment with the *Below 2 °C* and *1.5 °C high overshoot* pathways requires between 90–125 % more CO₂ reductions in this sector. In the oil production sector, the initiative goal for flaring is considerably more ambitious than the cost-effective *Below 1.5 °C high overshoot* pathway in which CO₂ emissions are phased out by around 2050 (Fig. 1b). Despite being considered cost-effective, reducing gas flaring in practice remains limited due to technical and regulatory barriers [1,55]. In the transport sector, the full implementation of 100 % electric vehicles by 2030 or 2040 is not feasible for some transport types in the IMAGE model (Fig. 1c, Supplementary Figure 3 and Supplementary Figure 4). Nonetheless, the ambitions of the passenger transport and truck initiatives align with the *2 °C* pathway until 2040. However, the reductions in truck emissions under the *Global Climate Initiatives* scenario fall short of the *Below 2 °C scenario* due to higher projected vehicle-kilometres driven (see Supplementary Figure 2). This shows the need for other transport measures such as modal shift or supporting changes in behaviour [52]. By 2030, the transport sector requires approximately 5 % additional reductions to stay on track with the *1.5 °C* pathway, increasing to 20 % by 2050. The ambition level of the international transport initiative is higher than that of the *Below 1.5 °C high overshoot* scenario, with emissions falling within the lower bound of the IPCC AR6 range (Fig. 1d). The ambition assumed in the *Global Climate Initiatives* scenario corresponds to the most ambitious scenario in the LTAG report [19]. Although an international shipping initiative exists, it is excluded from the analysis as it could not be quantified.

The goals of the cement and steel initiatives are aligned with the *Below 2 °C* pathway until 2030. The sectors these COP initiatives operate in represent around 30 % of industry CO₂ in 2020 (Fig. 1e). The IMAGE model shows that near-zero emissions in these sectors by 2030 is not feasible. This is consistent with findings by Bataille et al. [4], who highlight the challenge of achieving net-zero emissions as the global transition requires time and effort, particularly related to educating people in the workforce. These two COP initiatives do not cover other heavy industry sectors such as pulp & paper and chemicals or the light-industry sector. By 2030, a further 7 % is needed to remain on the *1.5 °C* pathway; by 2050, this gap increases to 30 % for the *Below 2 °C* pathway and 75 % for the *Below 1.5 °C high overshoot* pathway. The global deforestation pledge brings the AFOLU sector in line with the *Below 2 °C* or *1.5 °C high overshoot* pathways (Fig. 1f). However, this results in the same emissions level as under the *Current Policies* scenario, indicating that the pledge to halt and reverse forest loss is likely to be missed [36]. After 2030, ambition declines sharply, mainly due to the absence of additional measures such as afforestation and preventing CO₂ leakage to non-forested areas. The Global Methane Pledge for 2030 is highly ambitious and is only achieved in the model with the maximum reduction potential across all sectors and regions (Fig. 1f). If these assumptions are extended beyond 2030, the CH₄ emissions levels remain more ambitious compared to the *Below 1.5 °C high overshoot* pathway.

The COP initiatives do not comprehensively cover all greenhouse gases or economic sectors. Notably, N₂O, especially from agriculture, and fluorinated-gas emissions are excluded from the announced COP initiatives. In addition, the energy supply sector does not include CO₂ emissions from coal mining. In the energy-demand sectors, the COP initiatives do not cover emissions from buildings, chemicals, pulp & paper from the heavy-industry, light-industry, transport emissions from

domestic aviation and shipping, and trains.

3.2. Economy-wide results

At the global level, domestic implementation of all initiative goals by signatories is projected to substantially reduce global emissions relative to the *Current Policies* scenario and achieve alignment with the *Below 2 °C* pathway by 2030. However, additional efforts are required to align with the *Below 1.5 °C* pathway and to maintain alignment with both temperature pathways beyond 2030. If all initiative signatories were to fully implement the initiative goals domestically, global emissions are projected to decrease by 11 % relative to the *Current Policies* scenario by 2030, and 40 % by 2050. Notably, the Global Methane Pledge and 3R2E initiative together account for approximately 75 % of the total reductions by 2030 across all initiatives.

The *Signatories Climate Initiatives* is projected to reduce emissions by 2030 to levels consistent with the *Below 2 °C* pathway but fall short of the *Below 1.5 °C* pathway. To close this gap, an additional 5.5–8 % reductions in emissions is required. This would necessitate increasing the number of signatories, enhancing pledged ambitions, especially after 2030, and broadening sectoral coverage (see Discussion & Conclusions). By 2050, the emissions gap between the two Signatories scenarios with the *Below 2 °C* and *1.5 °C high overshoot* pathway widens to approximately 80 % and 82.5 %, respectively. If the USA were to withdraw from the COP initiatives they signed up to (3R2E, Coal phase-out, International aviation, Cooling, Steel, Methane, Deforestation), global emissions for the *Signatories Climate Initiatives* scenario would increase by almost 500 MtCO₂eq (see Supplementary Figure 5).

To assess the impact of different assumptions regarding the implementation of voluntary initiatives, we examine three sensitivity cases: 1) only assuming the Global Methane Pledge and Triple Renewable and Double Efficiency initiatives are implemented, 2) the United States does not implement the pledges of the initiatives it has signed up to, and 3) the Breakthrough Agenda buildings goals is made more concrete. Global greenhouse gas emissions vary only modestly under the different sensitivity scenarios (Fig. 3). Emissions increase when only the GMP/3R2E initiatives are implemented or when the United States withdraws, but decrease when the building goal is implemented globally. By 2030, *Global GMP/3R2E* reaches 45.8 GtCO₂-eq/yr, about 1.4 GtCO₂eq (~3 %) higher than in the *Global Climate Initiatives* scenario. *Signatories Climate Initiatives (excl. USA)* reaches 48.8 GtCO₂eq, about +0.44 Gt (~0.9 %) higher than the *Signatories* scenario (48.3 GtCO₂eq), though still around 9 % below *Current Policies*. In contrast, *Global Climate Initiatives (incl. Buildings)* reaches 44.5 GtCO₂eq, only 0.3 % lower than the emissions level in the *Global Climate Initiatives* scenario. By 2050, the same pattern persists: *Global GMP/3R2E*, *Global Climate (incl. Buildings)*, and *Signatories (excl. USA)* follow similar trends, with proportionally higher impacts. Overall, broader participation and sector coverage deepen and sustain reductions, while excluding a major emitter erodes the gains relative to the Signatories' baseline.

To show the impact of implementing the COP initiatives beyond the impact on global greenhouse gas emissions, the reductions between *Current Policies* and the *COP initiatives* were decomposed into energy intensity, conversion efficiency, CO₂ intensity, and non-CO₂ emissions (see Methods and Supplementary Material). The decomposition of global emissions reductions shows clear contrasts between the *Global Climate Initiatives* scenario and the temperature-aligned pathways (Fig. 4). Under the *Global Climate Initiatives*, reductions by 2050 are driven mainly by CO₂ intensity (42 %) and non-CO₂ emissions (62 %), with smaller contributions from energy intensity (17 %) and conversion efficiency (6 %). In comparison, the *Below 2 °C* (>67 %) and *Below 1.5 °C* (>50 %) pathways rely much more heavily on CO₂-intensity improvements and stronger conversion efficiency gains. In the *Below 2 °C* pathway, CO₂ intensity falls by about 120 percent by 2050—three times the reduction in the *Global Climate Initiatives*—while non-CO₂ emissions decline by 56 percent and energy intensity by 19 percent. The

Below 1.5 °C pathway shows even stronger changes, with energy intensity improving by 33 percent and CO₂ intensity by >400 %, while conversion efficiency improves only by about 3 percent. These results indicate that meeting temperature goals below 2 °C requires deeper CO₂ intensity reductions and stronger efficiency improvements than those projected under the current *Global Climate Initiatives*.

The outcomes of the Global Stocktake include eight Global Stocktake goals to keep the world on track toward limiting global temperature increase well below 2 °C or 1.5 °C. Our assessment of the COP initiative goals against these Global Stocktake indicators, translated into specific indicators, shows that while full implementation by 2030 aligns with 2 °C scenarios in many cases, and 1.5 °C scenario in certain cases, it remains insufficient to achieve net-zero emissions by 2050, which is essential for limiting warming to 1.5 °C (see Fig. 5). In addition, although the resulting renewable capacity and energy efficiency improvements exceed the level under the 2 °C and the renewable capacity also exceeds the 1.5 °C by 2030, they fall short by 2050 without stepping up climate ambition.

The first two stocktake goals and indicators on tripling renewable energy and doubling efficiency coincide with the goals of the 3R2E initiative. The goal to triple renewable energy by 2030 (Fig. 5a1), in the *Global GMP/3R2E* scenario, if both initiatives were globally implemented, would exceed the renewable capacity levels projected by the IMAGE model under both the *Below 2 °C* and *1.5 °C high overshoot* scenarios. By 2050, however, renewable capacity under the *Global GMP/3R2E* scenario falls below both temperature-aligned scenarios. In contrast, due to the higher number of initiatives, the *Global Climate Initiatives* scenario by 2050 is in line with the *Below 2 °C* scenario. The second stocktake goal is to double energy efficiency by 2030 (Fig. 5a2), which is projected to result in annual energy intensity improvements by 2030 falling between the levels of the *Below 2 °C* and *1.5 °C high overshoot* scenarios. Maintaining equivalent effort beyond 2030 results in somewhat higher annual improvements for the *Global Climate Initiatives* scenario compared to both temperature scenarios. The presented IPCC AR6 ranges (based on 9 models for energy efficiency, see Fig. 5) demonstrate that multiple cost-effective pathways exist to achieve the Paris goals, which vary, inter alia, in the balance between direct GHG abatement and energy efficiency improvements [13]. The majority of model scenarios included in the IPCC AR6 database representing cost-effective pathways consistent with well below 2 °C and 1.5 °C pathways (low and high overshoot), project a two- to sixfold increase in renewable capacity between 2020 and 2030, while improvements in energy efficiency over the same period range from no change to doubling (see Supplementary Figure 4). The coal phase-down under the *Global Climate Initiatives* scenario (Fig. 5b) is in line with the 2 °C

scenario by both 2030 and 2050; however, to align with the 1.5 °C scenario requires significantly greater ambition, particularly after 2030, when the *Below 1.5 °C high overshoot* pathway approaches zero.

Implementation of the COP initiatives results in lower energy-related CO₂ emissions by 2030 (Fig. 5c) compared to both the *Below 2 °C* and *Below 1.5 °C high overshoot* scenarios. However, neither the *Global Climate Initiatives* nor the *GMP/3R2E* scenario achieve net-zero emissions in the energy systems by 2050, which is essential to limiting temperature increase to below 1.5 °C (with high overshoot), and is achieved by all modelled scenarios in the IPCC AR6 database. A similar outcome (only inverted) is observed for the non-fossil primary energy indicator (Fig. 5d), which reflects transitioning away from fossil fuels. By 2030, non-fossil energy use under both COP initiatives scenarios is slightly higher than in the *Below 2 °C* and *Below 1.5 °C high overshoot* scenarios, but this trend reverses substantially by 2050. The 2030 level of the stocktake indicators representing accelerating low-emissions technologies (hydrogen, fossil with CCS, nuclear, and renewables), only differs slightly across the *Below 2 °C* and *1.5 °C high overshoot* scenarios, and both the COP Initiatives scenarios lie in between (Fig. 5e). The share of the different low-emissions technologies also does not differ much. By 2050, this indicator is not aligned with 2 °C and 1.5 °C pathways.

Among all COP initiatives, only one specifically targets non-CO₂ emissions, specifically CH₄ (Fig. 5f). Other non-CO₂ gases are not directly addressed. Given the high ambition of the 2030 methane pledge (see Sectoral results and Discussion & Conclusions), non-CO₂ emissions by 2030 fall below the levels projected under the 2 °C and 1.5 °C *high overshoot* scenarios. Assuming equivalent effort, this trend is the same but smaller through 2050. Additionally, the IPCC AR6 ranges reveal a trade-off between CO₂ and non-CO₂ mitigation, depending on cost assumptions and included implementation barriers. Finally, the CO₂ emissions indicator for road transport (Fig. 5g), representing the acceleration of road transport reductions, shows trends consistent with those found in the broader transport sector (see Sectoral results).

4. Discussion & conclusions

The announcement of voluntary climate initiatives during the last few Conferences of Parties (COPs) highlighted an emerging trend of interplay where the goals of these initiatives influence the outcomes of the Global Stocktake and COP decisions. In this context, this study assessed the combined impact of the voluntary climate initiatives announced around both the Glasgow and Dubai COPs, explicitly evaluating the direct effect on projected GHG emissions of signatory countries and Paris alignment of their aspirational goals.

Fig. 2. Global emissions pathways for Current policies, below 2 °C, below 1.5 °C and different Climate COP initiatives scenarios between 2010 and 2050. The IMAGE results are compared with the IPCC AR6 database [5]. The scenarios categories are: C1, representing a 50 % probability of limiting global warming to 1.5 °C with limited overshoot (grey bar); C2, representing 50 % probability of limiting warming to 1.5 °C with high overshoot (red bar); and a 67 % probability of limiting warming to below 2 °C (light blue bar) [22]. Source historical data: CEDS [6], EDGAR [15].

Fig. 3. Sensitivity scenarios comparing emissions levels by 2030 and 2050 if 1) only the GMP and 3R2E initiatives would be implemented, 2) the US would not implement their pledges in the initiatives, and 3) the buildings goal from the Breakthrough Agenda is concretised. The grey bars represent the signatories' implementation, and the green bars the full global implementation.

Fig. 4. Decomposition of reduction between Current Policies and COP Initiatives and below 2 °C and 1.5 °C scenarios for the years 2030, 2040, and 2050. The decomposition divides the reductions into CO₂ and non-CO₂, where the CO₂ reductions are further decomposed using the IPAT identity into energy intensity, conversion efficiency, and CO₂ intensity. The decomposition makes use of log-transformations, as reflected in log-scale y-axis.

When comparing global emission levels across the thematic areas under the aggregated ambitions of signatories to the COP initiatives, assuming domestic implementation of initiative targets, projections for 2030 to 2050 are more ambitious than those under the *Current Policies* scenario. If implemented, global emissions by 2030 are projected to decrease by about 11 % relative to the *Current Policies* scenario. Around 5–8 % additional reductions are required to close the gap with the 2 °C and 1.5 °C pathways. This indicates that simply implementing the initiatives worldwide is insufficient to close the global gap with pathways aligned with the Paris Agreement temperature goals, though it may suffice for individual countries (see Supplementary Figure 6).

If we assess the global aspirational goals of the COP initiatives, they are generally aligned with cost-effective 2 °C pathways at sectoral levels, as projected by the IMAGE model by 2030. However, the Global Methane Pledge and the international aviation initiative are even more ambitious compared to the 1.5 °C pathway. After 2030, the initiatives' pathways fall short of the 2 °C pathway, showing that increased ambition between 2030 and 2050 is required, both through domestic actions or non-state actions, and thus also of the initiatives themselves. Global implementation of the Methane Pledge and the 'Triple renewable energy/double energy efficiency' initiative together account for approximately 75 % of total reductions by 2030 across all 13 initiatives analysed in this study. If we assume equivalent effort after the target year of each initiative, aligning with the 2 °C and 1.5 °C pathways requires 35 % to 75 % additional emissions reductions by 2050.

The initiatives do not cover all economic sectors and greenhouse gases. They exclude goals for N₂O and fluorinated gas emissions, the buildings sector, pulp & paper, chemicals, light-industry sector, coal

mining emissions, and international shipping. Although COP initiatives exist for the buildings sector and international shipping, they lack quantifiable goals. In addition, voluntary climate initiatives that were not announced at COPs and could fill the gaps in thematic areas exist, such as the Global Alliance for Buildings and Construction, the Low Carbon Rail Transport Challenge, the Fashion Industry Charter for Climate Action and others. Furthermore, progress of some initiatives is insufficiently transparent and slow [26], supporting the goal of the COP30 Presidency to focus on existing and effective initiatives.

One important insight is the interplay between the goals of the COP initiatives and proliferation into the Global Stocktake and COP outcomes. It would be interesting to further explore this topic with the aim to find out the precise dynamics and actors involved. This research could build on existing work on the orchestration of non-state actors [8,28], focusing on the dynamics of the proliferation of goals and targets under the UNFCCC umbrella.

Although our results suggest that the ambitions of COP initiatives are generally aligned with a below 2 °C pathway by 2030, implementation is critical, and ambition must be translated into concrete actions. For this purpose, focus on individual sector, means of implementation (e.g. finance, capacity) and transparency are key [33]. On one hand, the effectiveness of COP initiatives is questioned as they demonstrate slow progress and a lack of sufficient reductions by individual actors. On the other hand, they represent a useful opportunity to bring together countries, cities, regions, and companies into a stronger coalition willing to continue robust climate action. These dynamics echo historical patterns, such as the widened participation of stakeholders after the failure of COP15 and the emergence of America's Pledge after the US

Fig. 5. Pathways of stocktake Indicators, representing suggested efforts from the outcomes of the Global Stocktake, as a result of the global implementation of the COP initiatives. The error ranges (vertical grey lines with horizontal caps) indicate the results from the IPCC AR6 database [5]. The scenarios categories are: C1, representing a 50 % probability of limiting global warming to 1.5 °C with limited overshoot; C2, representing 50 % probability of limiting warming to 1.5 °C with high overshoot; and a 67 % probability of limiting warming to below 2 °C [22]. The number of scenarios and corresponding models are shown in the table below, showing that not all models report the variables needed to calculate energy intensity improvement (primary energy, GDP (PPP)).

withdrawal from the Paris Agreement [18,27]. At present, climate negotiations and the multilateral system are challenged by mistrust, resistance to fossil fuel phase-outs, vested interests and geopolitical conflicts [30,31]. In this context of geopolitical uncertainty, rebuilding trust through coalitions within the UNFCCC alongside a stronger focus on delivering global and sectoral goals and commitments is crucial [30, 41,46].

The goals of the initiatives could serve as Paris aligned benchmarks for assessing the collective contribution in specific mitigation areas of current implemented policies and NDCs. Especially, as updated NDCs have been reported in 2025 to the Paris Agreement (see Supplementary Figure 7 for comparison with NDC pathways based on 2020 submissions). In addition, they serve as sectoral, greenhouse gas or technology roadmaps for achieving 2 °C or 1.5 °C pathways in specific thematic areas until 2050. If these areas would cover all greenhouse gases and all economic sectors, this could serve as a bottom-up ambition pathway toward the Paris goals. This roadmap could provide a starting point for an action infrastructure under the UNFCCC. Within such a framework, countries, subnational and non-state actors would need to collaborate to align their ambitions and concrete climate actions with the goals of the Paris agreement. For this purpose, the roadmap must be extended to include thematic areas not covered under current COP initiatives, such as agricultural N₂O. Certain existing goals and targets

should be made more concrete, particularly for buildings. Furthermore, it should accommodate differentiated ambition across countries, recognising that global climate goals relate differently to country-specific cost-effective pathways (see Supplementary Figure 6).

One critical issue is the design of the bottom-up scenarios used to set the goals for thematic areas. This choice needs to reflect the existence of multiple possible pathways to keep temperature increase well below 2 °C or 1.5 °C, as illustrated by the range of outcomes for the Triple Renewable/Double Efficiency goals across IPCC AR6 scenarios (see Supplementary Figure 8). This could be achieved by using the results from multiple models that together give the needed ranges and trade-offs among mitigations across sectors. In addition, they need to reflect feasible goals. For example, the Global Methane Pledge can be considered as one of the most ambitious goals among our selected initiatives. However, with no realistic implementation roadmap currently in place, the global goal can only be considered motivational and will likely face a significant implementation gap, seeing also that methane emissions have increased by 3.5 % between 2020 and 2023 [25]. If all methane-focused actions in the NDCs were implemented, with mitigation potentials far beyond the currently available technology, the GMP goal could just be met [29]. However, national methane action plans are found to have few quantitative targets or timelines, insufficient (<30 %) focus on agriculture, and no mention of regulatory frameworks or

financial incentives. In IMAGE, the GMP is achieved only if we assume the maximum potential of measures is implemented in all global regions and sectors.

For further research on voluntary climate initiatives, we suggest developing a methodology to assess the integrity of voluntary pledges in line with the integrity framework by the UN HLEG [17,49]. Such a methodology would need to include an assessment of the progress made by these initiatives since their inception, the credibility of their pledges based on the extent to which they are implementing current policies, and the technical, economic, and political feasibility of the pledges. This would require translating global commitments to country-specific targets that account for common but differentiated responsibilities, capabilities, and social- and economic conditions. Existing approaches can serve as a basis for this work [2,3,10,26]. The results could be incorporated into explorative scenarios that could illustrate the consequences of delayed implementation or reduced ambitions.

We conclude that while voluntary climate initiatives demonstrate potential, if implemented, to increase emission reductions beyond current implemented policies and narrow the gap with the Paris Agreement's temperature goals, significant gaps remain in the coverage of thematic areas, 1.5 °C ambition of individual initiative goals, and actual implementation. At the same time, the interplay between the voluntary initiatives and the Global Stocktake and COP outcomes serve as a guidance for deep sustained reductions by willing countries under the umbrella of the UNFCCC. To achieve this, it is essential to bridge these gaps by increasing ambition for certain goals, expanding thematic areas, and requiring concrete climate action plans.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Mark Roelfsema: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Ioannis Dafnomilis:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Michel den Elzen:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Mathijs Harmsen:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Formal analysis. **Harmen-Sytze de Boer:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Jonathan Doelman:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Detlef van Vuuren:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

Mark Roelfsema reports financial support was provided by Horizon Europe. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.egycc.2026.100237](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egycc.2026.100237).

Data availability

"PBL Netherlands Environmental Assessment Agency holds the proprietary rights to the IMAGE computer code; extensive documentation is provided at <https://models.pbl.nl/image>. The model is in the process of becoming open source, see <https://www.pbl.nl/en/publications/>

[the-image-strategy-document-2022-2027](https://www.pbl.nl/en/publications/the-image-strategy-document-2022-2027).

The downscaling to country signatories can be found at: https://github.com/imagepbl/downscaling/tree/main/COP_initiatives.

The results for each scenario for different variables used in this study and the data underlying Fig. 1 to 5, can be found at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17447556>.

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